

SEAMARK DELIVERABLE 3.2: BIOREFINERY PLANT IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

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Public summary of
confidential report

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Summary:

In general, sustainable seaweed farming is a nascent industry across Europe, and globally. Seaweed biorefineries are essential to successfully upscale the European seaweed supply chain. However, a lack of access to commercial-scale processing infrastructure has been a barrier for European farmers to scale supply.

Oceanium has developed a proprietary biorefinery technology (TRL7/8) that extracts and purifies high value bioactives (fucoïdan and beta-glucan, about 5% of seaweed dry weight); and the seaweed fibre (~33% of seaweed dry weight) that is being developed for food and materials use. The next step is to build a first-of-its-kind net-zero sustainable seaweed biorefinery in Europe.

This report demonstrates the concept design developed for a new seaweed biorefinery facility capable of processing approximately 2000 tonnes per annum, running production initially 10 hours per day, 5 days per week. Furthermore, these designs need to be replicable to help Oceanium meet its target of opening 6 additional biorefineries by 2028, as well as scalable to a capability of refining 10,000 tonnes of seaweed per year by 2031.

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